

Semantic modelling and publishing African Red Slip Ware as Linked Data

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Abstract

The African Red Slip Ware (ARS) is a central archaeological object type for the understanding of late antique world of ideas, their exchange and socio-economic history. The 3-year project ARS3D, funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF), started in February 2018 and aims to document, digitise and publish the relief-decorated ARS, located in the Römisch-Germanischen Zentralmuseum (RGZM). The ARS3D project will publish the facts and archaeological interpretations of these ARS objects. In this process the ARSs are 3D scanned and processed to create their 3D surrogates. These 3D models support archaeological interpretations which should be documented. Here we present our ontology that forms the structural fundament for the documentation and the underlying triplestore as data repository. The axioms are primarily based on CIDOC-CRM with few additions to fulfil our requirements. In addition, we included axioms to provide structure for storing meta- and para- information generated during the creation of 3D models. We have also included axioms from PROV-O, the W3C compliance ontology for structuring the provenance information of the 3D generation process. An interactive web application provides the graphical user interface of this ARS data repository. In this paper we consider data quality aspects for: 1) Provenance quality that affects the archaeological interpretations. 2) Archaeological factual quality on ARSs such as iconographical descriptions by bibliographic references and external resources, e.g. Icon Class to access the LOD cloud. 3) Identifying the provenance and storing chronological information.

Keywords: ?

Introduction

Archaeological methods are constantly under review as our technological abilities continue to develop. Archaeological research has gone through an evolutionary process and is currently in the middle of the digital transformation era. Archaeologists record, save, transmit and process machine-readable data via the `World Wide Web`. However, in order to move to the second wave of digitalisation they must analyse, enhance and use this data for machine-interpretation

using `Artificial Intelligence` and `Machine Learning` technologies (Wahlster 2017).

We started from an analogue era, in which research data was kept in books and collections, moving into the digital era, in which digitalisation and data publishing on the web sped up and we have now moved past the semantic era, characterised by semantic modelling and the publication of Linked Data. We therefore end up in a knowledge era, analysing and creating new knowledge through the machine (Thiery 2019a).

Archaeological domains are on different levels (figure 1) of methodological development: for example,

Figure 1. Archaeology 4.0, Florian Thiery (CC BY 4.0) via Wikimedia Commons

African Red Slip Ware (ARS), a special type of ancient ceramics, is well documented in written texts and has also taken the first steps towards the digital era. To continue this evolution, the African Red Slip Ware digital research project (ARS3D) will enable ARS to move into the semantic era making possible new analyses and understandings of this ceramic data.

In this paper, therefore, we propose a semantic modelling and publishing strategy for African Red Slip Ware. We build on a CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM) ceramics modelling (Gruber and Smith 2015), by extending CIDOC CRM to cater to our specific needs by adopting a data publishing strategy, using Berners-Lee's (2006) idea of Linked Open Data (LOD). This means that the data is anchored in the Linked Open Data Cloud and connected to relevant related datasets to provide further context for digital archaeological research.

We will start with a general introduction to Samian Ware and African Red Slip Ware (section 2), semantic technologies in cultural heritage (section 3) and publishing strategies in the World Wide Web (section 4). This will be followed by a description of the digital workflow circle in the ARS3D project (section 5).

2. Samian Ware

Samian Ware is a particular category of Roman fine pottery which is comprised of clay with a glossy surface slip, having a characteristic colour range from 'pale orange' to 'bright red'. Depending on the place of manufacture, it can also go by other names, including Terra Sigillata, Arretine Ware, or, in our case, African Red Slip Ware. Production of Samian Ware started in the 1st century AD and was maintained

with different local emphases until the later Imperial period. Important production centres were located in Italy, south, east and central Gaul, as well as northern Africa, and Samian Ware was exported from there in large quantities to the Roman Empire. Highly standardised types like bowls and plates were decorated in different styles and techniques.

In order to standardise the recording and publishing of Samian ware, the project 'Samian Research' (Mees 2018) composed a suite of databases concerned with Samian Ware on their Website.

2.1 African Red Slip Ware

African Red Slip Ware (also called Late Roman A and B, Late Roman Red Ware, Chiara A, C, D, Hayes 1972: 13) was produced predominantly in the provinces of Africa Proconsularis and Byzacena (Tunisia) from the late 1st century to the 7th century AD. The products of the North African workshops became very popular for domestic use and exportation to the Mediterranean (Hayes 1972: 15-17).

Characteristic of the African Red Slip Ware is its rich pictorial decoration. Decoration was modelled either in relief (applique) or moulded relief decoration. Through the combination of different figurative motifs, a very varied spectrum of individual depictions and narrative scenes were created. This is particularly the case for highly standardised types such as the Hayes 53 A (bowl) or Hayes 56 (rectangular plates) in the period from ca. 360-430 AD (Hayes 1972: 13-14, 211-214).

The monograph of J. Hayes "Late Roman Pottery" from 1972 (Hayes 1972) is still regarded as the standard reference for the typological and chronological documentation of African Red Slip Ware. Among oth-

ers, J. W. Salomonson (1962), M. Armstrong (1993), F. Bejaoui (1997) and S. von Löwenstein (2015: 397-823) studied the motifs of the appliques and reliefs.

2.2 ARS at the RGZM and the AR3D project

The Römisch-Germanisches Zentralmuseum - Leibniz Research Institute for Archaeology (RGZM) in Mainz owns a large collection of ARS: 336 objects including 100 complete objects, 152 fragments, 36 moulds, 6 stamps, 36 lamps, and 6 lamp moulds. These were mainly produced between the 3rd c. AD - 6th c. AD in North Africa (Tunisia) and were traded throughout whole Roman Empire. The appliques show mythological, Old/New Testament scenes, circus, arena and hunting depictions as well as fish and plant images.

The first cataloguing of the RGZM collection was done by Konrad Weidenmann. In 1990 he summarised the highlights of the collection under the title “Spätantike Bilder des Heidentums und Christentums” (Weidenmann 1990). Each colour photo is accompanied by a short, predominantly interpretative description. Additional authors dealt with the Mainz collection considering different scientific questions (e.g. von Löwenstein 2015: 397-823; Atlante 1981). Digital photographs were taken of all the objects and are accessible via an internal database. However, without machine readable, findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable FAIR data, machines cannot be used properly to help researchers to find unexpected results.

To enable this, the African Red Slip Ware digital project was founded in 2018-2020 by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) and is carried out by the Hochschule Mainz University of Applied Sciences and RGZM, leading ARS into Archaeology 4.0.

The overall aim of the ARS3D project is to provide the research community with innovative and sustainable access to largely digital, unpublished object types to enable not only the establishment of new research questions, but also to set documentation standards by 3D documentation for a multi-perspective analysis of a central Late Antique object type.

3 Semantic technologies in cultural heritage

The term ‘Semantic Web’ was coined by Tim Berners-Lee who describes it as a web of data that can be processed by machines through the explicit semantic definition of data, thereby making this information machine readable (Berners-Lee, Hendler and Lassila 2001). Over the years the migration of static information over the web to semantic machine readable information has touched every academic field, including that of Cultural Heritage.

Cultural Heritage comprising communities such as galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAM) embraces a very diverse field of disciplines. Although all communities within GLAMs share common goals and interests, they portray very diverse methodologies and approaches. However, a common semantic framework of CIDOC CRM binds them together for their documentation activities. Published by the International Council of Museums (ICOM) Documentation committee (CIDOC) in 2001, the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM) was accepted as an ISO standard in 2006 (Isaksen 2011).

CIDOC CRM is considered to be the main domain ontology in Cultural Heritage. With the primary goal of smooth information exchange and integration between heterogeneous sources of Cultural Heritage information, the CRM provides a common semantic framework with required key concepts and defines the underlying semantics of the data schemata and document structures.

Among the CIDOC CRM compatible models and collaborations generally referred to as its ‘extensions’, the ARS3D ontology has theorems based on CRM_{inf}, CRM_{dig} and CRM_{sci}. CRM_{inf} is a formal ontology that represents metadata about argumentation and inference-making. It uses the same formalisation of knowledge representation as CIDOC CRM, along with concepts required to represent argumentation based on archaeological information (Stead and Doerr 2015). CRM_{dig} is the formal ontology that represents the provenance information of digitisation and synthesizing to create digital models through different technologies (Doerr and Theodoridou 2011). Lastly, CRM_{sci} is the formal ontology to represent scientific observation, measurements and processed data (Doerr et al. 2018).

CIDOC CRM is the standardised semantic frame-

work that laid the foundation for other cultural heritage applications. To list a few, WissKI is an open source virtual resource environment and content management system for Cultural Heritage, that enriches information through semantic formalisation and uses CIDOC CRM as its base ontology (Scholz and Goerz 2012). Similarly, the Arches inventory system, developed by the Getty Conservation Institute and World Monuments Fund, implements CIDOC CRM and its extensions to provide explicit semantics to the heritage information system inventories (Myers, Dalgity and Avramides 2016).

4 Publishing archaeological data in the WWW

In ancient times, the phrase ‘Hic sunt dracones’ (here be dragons) was used to describe areas which are unknown to the cartographer (Wuttke 2019). Today many of our digital data is neither findable nor openly accessible which results in modern unknown ‘data dragons’ (Thiery et al. 2019b). These data dragons lack connections to other datasets. To overcome these shortcomings, a set of techniques, standards and recommendations is used (Thiery et al. 2019a; Data Dragon 2019) and described below:

As mentioned in section 3, Tim Berners-Lee established his concept of the ‘Semantic Web’ using Open Data (Auer et al. 2007), to describe web resources and links as well as usable, machine readable interfaces. Further, the ‘FAIR principles’ introduced in 2016 (Wilkinson et al. 2016), mean that research data and its metadata has to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). However, publishing data as unique identifiers on the net, Hypertext Transfer Protocol Uniform Resource Identifiers (HTTP URIs), by using links to other resources is on little use unless the data is open and usable. Assuming that it is then they end up in the LOD (Hausenblas and Boram Kim 2015) and Linked Open Usable Data (LOUD) principles (Sanderson 2019). All of these techniques can be combined in a ‘7 Sphere Data’ model, introduced by Thiery (2019b).

Initial approaches for publishing archaeological data in the Semantic Web were adopted in Leif Isaksen’s PhD (Isaksen 2011) on ‘Archaeology and the Semantic Web’. Furthermore, in the research of ceramics,

Florian Thiery proposed an idea to publish South Gaulish Samian Ware as interoperable LOD at AG CAA and CAA International 2014 (Thiery 2013; Thiery 2014), to create an ‘Archaeological Linked Data Cloud’ (Thiery 2019a) as part of the huge ‘Linked Data Cloud’ (McCrae 2019).

Nowadays, an array of Linked Open Data projects from the humanities and the archaeological domain are available on the web. They come from a huge community of specialists, e.g. Linked Pasts (Grossner and Hill 2017; Grossner 2019), providing user-friendly infrastructure solutions and widely used RDF web resources. Popular examples for the archaeological domain are: Nomisma.org (Gruber 2018) for the research of coins, Kerameikos.org (Gruber and Smith 2015) for the research of ceramics and Open Context (Kansa 2007) for the publication of individual research data on the web.

Beyond that, ideas of modelling hidden assumptions (Thiery and Mees 2018) in archaeological research data and modelling uncertainty (Unold, Thiery and Mees 2019; Tolle and Wigg-Wolf 2015) are currently being developed by several world-wide interdisciplinary research groups (Thiery et al. 2019a).

5 The digital circle

The ARS3D digitalisation and publishing process (figure 2) can be described in a digital circle: produce a 3D digitalisation via a 3D scanner, create a semantic description via semantic modelling using common ontologies, edit the data in a 3D geometry tool and publish the data in a web portal, to enable digital research to gain new perspectives on ARS. The following

Figure 2. ARS3D’s digital circle (CC BY 4.0)

Figure 3. The ARS3D ontology (CC BY 4.0)

sections will give a deeper insight into the steps of the circle.

5.1 Digitalisation

For scanning purposes we are using a structured light projection scanner (SLS) to digitise the ARS and manufacturing objects. Depending on the object size, different measuring volumes are used. We are also using the Structure from Motion (SfM) technique for surface texture recording, using a professional camera body for taking the photos. In order to make the capture of the objects as efficient as possible, a special concept and method has been created, to enable a correct projection of the obtained texture onto the corresponding 3D data. This process is part of the ARS3D project as well, which is not described here in detail. However, more information on how to record cultural heritage objects in the context of COSCHKR can be found in Wefers et al. (2017).

5.2 Semantic Description

As stated, the ARS3D Ontology relies heavily on the concepts of CIDOC-CRM and its extensions, mainly CRMinf, CRMdigo and CRMsci (fig. 3). The formalisations of these concepts are required while documenting the archaeological interpretations of the ARSs hosted at the RGZM. In addition, the ontology has included other required concepts and roles beyond those provided in the CRMs.

In short, we are creating an ARS3D ontology to fulfil our particular needs (e.g. geometry provenance information, individual observations and interpretations, links to external thesauri) as a structural foundation for the documentation. Our ontology is based on CIDOC CRM, CRM extensions and an ontology for provenance information, here PROV-O, with a few additions (figure 3).

The ontology is based on two types of objects: 'African Red Slip Ware Objects' (ARS); and 'Manufacturing Objects' (MO). In our general model (figure 4, left), ARS and MO contain features which can be related to other features or features on other objects, or can be grouped into scenes and observations of depictions, which can then be used as part of an interpretation argument.

An ARS entity (e.g. object) can be characterised (figure 4, right) using CIDOC CRM and ARS extension classes by an identifier (crm:E42), provenance (crm:E53), chronological information (crm:E4, crm:E63), material (crm:E57), shape (ars:Shape), condition (ars:Condition_Type) and the manufacturing object used (ars:Manufacturing_Object_Type).

A special documentation entity is a statement (figure 5, left) which documents narrations (types) that are mostly documented in books. A statement (ars:-Statement) describes e.g. the statement type (crm:E55)

Figure 4. AThe general model (left), object meta-data (right) (CC BY 4.0)

Figure 5. Statement metadata (left), features and scenes (right) (CC BY 4.0)

with its classification type (String), the associated book (crm:E31) and some specific comments. These statements imply that not only new observations and interpretations are created, but also existing (past) interpretations produced by scholars in the literature will be related to these, so that the model could provide the users with elements useful for reconstructing the history of the research and interpretation of each specimen.

One object (ars:ARS/MO) consists of many features (crm:E25), which can be related to many other features and which may also have multiple observations (crm:S4). Features can also be grouped in scenes (ars:Scene), figure 5, right.

A feature observation (crm:S4) is assigned to multiple observation items stored in an hierarchy, e.g. Human→Man/Woman, which are acting (crm:E7) in certain ways, e.g. running, and/or having certain conditions (crm:E3), e.g. bearded, figure 6, left.

An individual interpretation (ars:Interpretation) is based on a collection of arguments (crm:I1) referring to multiple feature observations (crm:S4), multiple stated statements (ars:Statement) and/or multiple geometry processes, figure 6, right.

Individual interpretations are based on CRMInf and CRMsci extensions, as well as ARS3D specific classes and properties

Metadata about the scanning process, e.g. scanning device, editor, camera, or resolution parameters, will be added afterwards using the CRMdig extension. Digital processes like extracting geometry derivatives, e.g. cutting out geometry by segmentation and annotation processes, flattening of appliques into 2.5D, and its parameters and resulting files are modelled using an extended CRMdig model.

5.2.1 Use Case O.39675

As an example of the application of the described CIDOC CRM and ARS extension (section 5.2), Object O.39675 has been characterised by the following entities and instances shown below (table 1).

Using 'object statement', we define the object type (for example, bowl O.39675 has the type Hayes 53a). Each type is documented in a particular publication (Hayes 1972) on a particular page (Hayes 1972: 78-82). This assignment allows archaeologists to easily compare the different forms and types based on common determination literature.

Figure 6. Observation metadata (left), interpretation and arguments (right) (CC BY 4.0)

Table 1. Object metadata of O.39675

property	individual	class type
rdf:type		
crm:P44_has_condition	complete	
crm:P1_is_identified_by	O.39675	crm:E42
crm:P53_has_former_or_current_location	RGZM	crm:E53
crm:P2_has_type	potter wheel made	crm:E12
crm:P2_has_type	clay with slip	crm:E57
ars:hasShape	bowl	ars:Shape
crm:P8_took_place_on_or_within;crm:P86i_contains	Late Antiquity;4./5 AD	crm:E4;crm:E63

In this instance, the object contains multiple appliques (features) and is divided into multiple scenes (figure 7). On the one hand we have Scene 2 (three men and kiln/furnace with three escaping figures). On the other hand we have Scene 1, described below. Two trees divide the scenes although these will not be described in the following example.

After modelling all the data on the object in general, the `observation` of the features follows, in this case two of the appliques on the bowl O.39675. Observations include what kind of (human) type they have,

what actions they perform, and what condition they have. Of course, we are aware that even observation cannot be objective. For this reason, it is possible to add several observations to each feature, which might have completely different meanings and thus lead to different interpretations. In our example, the activity of the woman can be seen in two observations: O3 Woman clutching the hem of man's coat in her left hand or O4: Woman touching man's coat; this naturally leads to two different observations of the man: O1: Man clutched by a woman behind him on his

Figure 7. O.39675 with its features and scenes, left: photo by Lübke & Wiedemann, Leonberg with annotations from Florian Thiery, right: (CC BY 4.0))

Figure 8. Scene 1 with applique 1A and 1B, photo by Lübke & Wiedemann, Leonberg

coat or O2: Man touched by a woman on his coat.. Referring to figure 8, we can suggest feature observations, table 2.

Based on the different observations, various interpretations can be suggested. Some observations are

used as arguments for a certain interpretation. As an argument for the interpretation of 'Joseph and Potiphar's wife' (Gen. 39, 7-20) the observation that the man is having his coat clutched by the woman is decisive. The alternative interpretation 'Christ is healing a woman with an issue of blood' (Matth. 9, 18-22) is based on the observation that the woman merely touches the man's coat.

To summarise, the two mentioned interpretations are shown in table 3.

5.2.2 Use Case O.41423

In addition to complete vessels or fragments bearing appliques, the Mainz collection also includes moulds for entire plates or, as here, individual appliques. Similar to the appliques, the modelling of the mould starts from the object, O.41423, figure 9, table 4.

The observation of the features, in this case the

Table 2. Evaluation results for charcoal-burning platform detection in SkyEye with an MCL dataset (a thousand pixels per class)

observation ID	type	instance	action/condition
O1	Human	Man	beard (E3)
	Human	Man	walking to the right (E7)
	Human	Man	clutched by a woman behind him by his coat (E7)
O2	Human	Man	beard (E3)
	Human	Man	walking to the right (E7)
	Human	Man	touched by a woman on his coat (E7)
O3	Human	Woman	dressed with garment (E3)
	Human	Woman	crouching on her knees (E7)
	Human	Woman	clutching the hem of man's coat in her left hand (E7)
O4	Human	Woman	dressed with garment (E3)
	Human	Woman	crouching on her knees (E7)
	Human	Woman	touched man's coat (E7)

negative elements (mould), also starts with the description of the character of the (human) type, the actions they perform and the condition they are in, table 5.

5.3 Geometry Tool

Scanned and textured 3D-models (section 5.1) of the RGZM ARS collection will be published in an interactive web viewer (ARS3D Geometry Browser), based on 3DHOP (Potenziani et al. 2015). The viewer allows an interactive feature selection.. This selection is used to cut out the selected object part from the point cloud via specialised server services (cf. Lange and Unold 2015). This geometry, e.g. applique, is able to be unfolded into 2.5D. The desired goal of the geometry

Figure 9. Mould fragment, photo by Sabine Steidl

tool is to facilitate researchers to compare possibly similar appliques. This part of the project is still under development (Justus, Atorf and Boochs 2019).

Table 3. Interpretations of O.39675

interpretation ID	interpretation	argument
I1 (Gen. 39, 7-20)	Joseph and Potiphar's wife	O1 + O3
I2 (Matth. 9, 18-22)	Woman with an issue of blood – Christ is healing a woman with an issue of blood	O2 + O4

Table 4. Object metadata of O.39675

property	individual	class type
rdf:type		ars:Manufacturing_Object
crm:P1_is_identified_by	O.41423	crm:E42
crm:P53_has_former_or_current_location	RGZM	crm:E53
crm:P2_has_type	plaster	crm:E57
ars:hasShape	mould	ars:Shape
crm:P8_took_place_on_or_within;crm:-P86i_contains	Late Antiquity;4./5 AD	crm:E4;crm:E63
crm:P44_has_condition	fragment	ars:Condition_Type

Table 5. Feature observations of O.39675

observation ID	type	instance	action/condition
O1	Human	Man	beard (E3)
O1	Human	Man	standing facing front (E7)
O1	Human	Man	holding a knife in his hand (E7)
O1	Human	Man	holding Man's_2 head down on an altar (E7)
O2	Human	Man	kneeling before an altar (E7)
O2	Human	Man	head held down by Man_1 (E7)

5.4 Publishing and Linked Data

Individual terms (e.g. period: late antiquity), which can be re-used as keywords by other repositories are linked via `ars:external_reference` to a `skos:Concept`, available in a published SKOS (Miles and Bechhofer 2009) thesaurus. Fortunately, the Linked Data Cloud offers a lot of concepts which can be used as keywords to describe our ARS collection, e.g. chronology (ChronOntology 2019; PeriodO 2019), object and feature description (Getty 2017; Iconclass 2015), places (GeoNames 2019; Pleiades 2019), literature (DNB 2019), and special archaeological terms (Thiery and Engel 2016). `Joseph`, the son of Jacob (Old Testament), can be described as Joseph (biblical character) in Getty (2004) or as 71D (Joseph) in Iconclass (2011).

At the RGZM, the `Meta-Index` (meta) is used as a central access point to enable a global search across distributed databases at the RGZM, based on Linked Data principles. Metas' core concept comprises a central index related to the SKOS-ontology. This extends to RGZM specific needs, a Linked Data Hub for aligning the data of the distributed databases by index terms, represented in different languages, and with descriptions which are structured hierarchically, semantically, by type and by label. `Meta` links its terms to external SKOS concepts in order to resolve

ambiguities (Thiery, Mees and Heinz 2018). A search query for Joseph would, therefore, retrieve all connected objects like O.39675.

The publishing of FAIR data is an important issue for the ARS3D project. The described and annotated 3D-data will be published in a free and openly accessible web portal. Moreover, the whole data graph stores in a triplestore, will be accessible by its SPARQL endpoint interface. Furthermore, resources for objects, features, statements and interpretations are accessible via an API as Sphere 7 Data (Thiery 2019b) for the coding and research community.

6 Digital research, Conclusion and Outlook

Our pilot project provides a platform for supplementing other collections and thus significantly increases the use of this type of material in research projects and educational programmes. It establishes new standards for the classification and determination of appliques and enables new digital research approaches, e.g. manufacturing technique or the combinations of features and narratives. In the long-term, the dataset created in the project has the potential to form the basis for a scientific engagement on a European level. Our project is

a first attempt at modelling and publishing ARS data as a starting point for further scientific discussion. The more collections that are digitised and catalogued according to ARS3D guidelines, the greater the value for research.

The combination of 3D models and modelled archaeological metadata allows scientists worldwide to conduct their own research on the ARS collection of the RGZM, and enables them to develop new research questions at any time. The disclosure of the observations used for the interpretation of the features allows a value-free approach.

In the future, the ARS3D data should be inter-linked with other LOD resources in the Linked Open Data Cloud, e.g. *kerameikos* (Gruber 2018), to extend

their ontology and publish our data, as done so far for coins in *nomisma* (Tolle and Wigg-Wolf 2015).

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References

- Armstrong, M A 1993** A Thesaurus of Applied Motives on African Red Slip Ware. New York: New York University, Graduate School of Arts and Sciences.
- Atlante 1981** Atlante delle forme ceramiche I, Ceramica fina Romana nel bacino mediterraneo, medio e tardo impero. Enciclopedia Italiana. Italia.
- Auer, S, Bizer, C, Kobilarov, G, Lehmann, J, Cyganiak, R and Ives, Z 2007** DBpedia: A Nucleus for a Web of Open Data. In: Aberer, K., Choi, K.-S., Noy, N., Allemang, D., Lee, K.-I., Nixon, L., Golbeck, J., Mika, P., Maynard, D., Mizoguchi, R., Schreiber, G., and Cudré-Mauroux, P. (eds.) *The Semantic Web. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*. 2007 Springer Berlin Heidelberg. pp. 722–735.
- Bejaoui, F 1997** Ceramique et religion chretienne : les thèmes bibliques sur la sigillée africaine. Tunis: Inst. Nat. du Patrimoine.
- Berners-Lee, T 2006** Linked Data - Design Issues. 27 July 2006. Available at <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html> [Last accessed 4 April 2019].
- Berners-Lee, T, Hendler, J and Lassila, O 2001** The Semantic Web, *Scientific American*, 284(5): 34–43. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/scientificamerican0501-34>.
- ChronOntology 2019** ChronOntology. 2019. Available at <https://chronontology.dainst.org/> [Last accessed 17 July 2019].
- Data Dragon 2019** Data Dragon – Hic sunt dracones! SIG on Semantics and LOUD in Archaeology. Available at <http://datadragon.link/> [Last accessed 22 July 2019].
- DNB 2019** DNB - Linked Data Service. DNB - Linked Data Service, 3 July 2019. Available at <https://www.dnb.de/EN/lids> [Last accessed 17 July 2019].
- Doerr, M, Kritsotaki, A, Rousakis, Y, Hiebel, G and Theodoridou, M 2018** Definition of the CRMsci. An Extension of CIDOC-CRM to support scientific observation.
- Doerr, M and Theodoridou, M 2011** CRMdig: A Generic Digital Provenance Model for Scientific Observation *TaPP*(11): 20–22.
- GeoNames 2019** GeoNames. 2019. Available at <https://www.geonames.org/> [Last accessed 17 July 2019].
- Getty 2004** Joseph (biblical character). 2004. Available at <http://www.getty.edu/cona/CONAIconographyRecord.aspx?iconid=901000525>.
- Getty 2017** Getty Vocabularies as LOD (Getty Research Institute). 26 October 2017. Available at <http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/lo/> [Last accessed 17 July 2019].
- Grossner, K 2019** A Emerging Linked Pasts Network. Linked Pasts, 21 March 2019. Available at <http://linkedpasts.github.io> [Last accessed 22 July 2019].
- Grossner, K and Hill, T 2017** From Linking Places to a Linked Pasts Network.
- Gruber, E 2018** Linked Open Data for Numismatic Library, Archive and Museum Integration. In: Matsu-moto, M. and Uleberg, E. (eds.) *CAA2016. Oceans of Data. Proceedings of the 44th Conference on Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology*. 2018 Oxford: Archaeopress. pp. 55–62.
- Gruber, E and Smith, T J 2015** Linked Open Greek Pottery. In: Giligny, F., Costa, L., Moscati, P., and Robert, S. (eds.) *CAA2014. 21st Century Archaeology. Concepts, methods and tools. Proceedings of the 42nd Annual Conference on Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology*. 2015 Oxford: Archaeopress. pp. 205–214.
- Hausenblas, M and Boram Kim, J G 2015** 5-star Open Data. 5 OPEN DATA, 31 August 2015. Available at <http://5stardata.info/en/> [Last accessed 4 April 2019].
- Hayes, J W 1972** Late Roman pottery. London: British School at Rome.
- Iconclass 2011** 71D (JOSEPH). September 2011.
- Iconclass 2015** Iconclass. 18 September 2015. Available at <http://www.iconclass.org/help/lo/> [Last accessed 17 July 2019].
- Isaksen, L 2011** Archaeology and the Semantic Web. phd. University of Southampton.
- Justus, C, Atorf, P and Boochs, F 2019** Gewinnung realitätsnaher virtueller Modelle als Grundlage für die Erkennung von Ähnlichkeiten. In: *Photogrammetrie - Laserscanning - Optische 3D-Messtechnik: Beiträge der Oldenburger 3D-Tage 2019*. Berlin: Wichmann. pp. 250–258.
- Kansa, E 2007** Publishing Primary Data on the World Wide Web: Opencontext.org and an Open Future for the Past. *Technical Briefs in Historical Archaeology*. 2 pp.1–11.
- Lange, F and Unold, M 2015** Semantisch angereicherte 3D-Messdaten von Kirchenräumen als Quellen für die geschichtswissenschaftliche Forschung, DOI: https://doi.org/10.17175/sb001_015.

- von Löwenstein, S 2016** Mythologische Darstellungen auf Gebrauchsgegenständen der Spätantike. Die appliken- und reliefverzierte Sigillata C3/C4. In: Römisch-Germanisches Museum Archäologische Gesellschaft in Köln, R.-G.M. /Archäologische G. in (ed.) Kölner Jahrbuch für Vor- und Frühgeschichte/ Kölner Jahrbuch Band 48 (2015). p.
- McCrae, J P 2019** The Linked Open Data Cloud. 2019. Available at <https://lod-cloud.net/> [Last accessed 11 August 2018].
- Mees, A 2018** Was there a Difference between Roman ‘Civil’ and ‘Military’ Samian (terra sigillata) Market Supply? Finding answers with statistical distribution analysis methods, *Internet Archaeology*, (50) . DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11141/ia.50.16>.
- Miles, A and Bechhofer, S 2009** SKOS Simple Knowledge Organization System Reference. 18 August 2009. Available at <https://www.w3.org/TR/2009/REC-skos-reference-20090818/> [Last accessed 11 August 2018].
- Myers, D, Dalgity, A and Avramides, I 2016** The Arches heritage inventory and management system: a platform for the heritage field, Myers and Mario Santana Quintero, D. (ed.) *Journal of Cultural Heritage Management and Sustainable Development*, 6(2): 213–224. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JCHMSD-02-2016-0010>.
- PeriodO 2019** PeriodO – Periods, Organized. 2019. Available at <https://perio.do/en/> [Last accessed 17 July 2019].
- Pleiades 2019** Pleiades. Pleiades, 2019. Available at <https://pleiades.stoa.org/> [Last accessed 17 July 2019].
- Potenziani, M, Callieri, M, Dellepiane, M, Corsini, M, Ponchio, F and Scopigno, R 2015** 3DHOP: 3D Heritage Online Presenter, *Computers & Graphics*, 52: 129–141. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cag.2015.07.001>.
- Salomonson, J W 1962** Late-Roman Earthenware with Relief Decoration Found in Northern-Africa and Egypt. *Oudheidkundige mededelingen uit het Rijksmuseum van Oudheden te Leiden*, 43.1962: 53-95.
- Sanderson, R 2019** LOUD: Linked Open Usable Data. 28 May 2019. Available at <https://linked.art/loud/> [Last accessed 5 April 2019].
- Scholz, M and Goerz, G 2012** WissKI: A Virtual Research Environment for Cultural Heritage, *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence and Applications*, 1017–1018. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-098-7-1017>.
- Stead, S and Doerr, M 2015** CRMinf: the Argumentation Model An Extension of CIDOC-CRM to support argumentation.
- Thiery, F 2013** Semantic Web und Linked Data: Generierung von Interoperabilität in archäologischen Fachdaten am Beispiel römischer Töpferstempel. Master Thesis. Mainz: Fachhochschule Mainz. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.292979>.
- Thiery, F 2014** Linking Potter, Pots And Places: A Lod Approach To Samian Ware DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.292975>.
- Thiery, F 2019a** Archaeology 4.0: Archaeology in the Third Era of Computing, LINKED GEODESY Working Papers, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2629595>.
- Thiery, F 2019b** Sphere 7 Data: LOUD and FAIR Data for the Research Community, LINKED GEODESY Working Papers, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2643469>.
- Thiery, F and Engel, T 2016** The Labelling System: The Labelling System: A Bottom-up Approach for Enriched Vocabularies in the Humanities. In: Campana, S., Scopigno, R., Carpentiero, G., and Cirillo, M. (eds.) CAA2015. Keep the Revolution Going. Proceedings of the 43rd Annual Conference on Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology. 2016 Oxford: Archaeopress. pp. 259–268.
- Thiery, F and Mees, A 2018** Taming the chronology of South Gaulish Samian found at Hadrian’s Wall and the German Limes using Linked Open Data DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1469298>.
- Thiery, F, Mees, A and Heinz, G 2018** RGZM-Meta-Index: A central Linked Data Hub for aligning distributed databases DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2222237>.
- Thiery, F, Trognitz, M, Gruber, E, Tolle, K and Wigg-Wolf, D 2019a** CAA SIG on ‘Semantics and LOUD in Archaeology’ DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3337979>.
- Thiery, F, Trognitz, M, Gruber, E and Wigg-Wolf, D 2019b** Hic sunt dracones! the modern unknown Data Dragons DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3345711>.
- Tolle, K and Wigg-Wolf, D 2015** Uncertainty Handling for Ancient Coinage. In: Giligny, F., Djindjian, F., Costa, L., Moscati, P., and Robert, S. (eds.) CAA2014.

21st Century Archaeology. Concepts, methods and tools. Proceedings of the 42nd Annual Conference on Computer Applications and Quantitative Methods in Archaeology. 2015 Oxford: Archaeopress. pp. 171–178.

Unold, M, Thiery, F and Mees, A 2019 Academic Meta Tool. Ein Web-Tool zur Modellierung von Vagheit, Die Modellierung des Zweifels – Schlüsselideen und -konzepte zur graphbasierten Modellierung von Unsicherheiten. [Ausgewählte Beiträge der Tagung 19.-20.01.2018 an der Akademie der Wissenschaften und der Literatur, Mainz] Hg. von Andreas Kuczera / Thorsten Wübbena / Thomas Kollatz. Wolfenbüttel 2019. (= Zeitschrift für digitale Geisteswissenschaften / Sonderbände: 4). DOI: https://doi.org/10.17175/sb004_004.

Wahlster, W 2017 Artificial Intelligence as the driver of the second wave of digitalization. 26 September 2017. Available at <https://www.vdmimpulse.org/article/-/article/render/156223> [Last accessed 17 July 2019].

Wefers, S, Karmacharya, A, Boocks, F and Heinz, G 2017 How to optimally record cultural heritage objects? Decision support through connected knowledge. In: Bienert, A. (ed.) EVA Berlin 2017: elektronische Medien & Kunst, Kultur und Historie: Konferenzband: 24. Berliner Veranstaltung der internationalen EVA-Serie: electronic media and visual arts: 8.-10. November 2017, Kunstgewerbemuseum am Kulturforum Potsdamer Platz, Berlin. 2017 Berlin: Staatliche Museen zu Berlin - Preussischer Kulturbesitz. pp. 63–67.

Weidemann, K 1990 Spätantike Bilder: des Heidentums und Christentums. Mainz: Verlag des Römisch-Germanischen Zentralmuseums.

Wilkinson, M D, Dumontier, M, Aalbersberg, Ij J, Appleton, G, Axton, M, Baak, A, Blomberg, N, Boiten, J-W, da Silva Santos, L B, Bourne, P E, Bouwman, J, Brookes, A J, Clark, T, Crosas, M, Dillo, I, Dumon, O, Edmunds, S, Evelo, C T, Finkers, R, Gonzalez-Beltran, A, Gray, A J G, Groth, P, Goble, C, Grethe, J S, Heringa, J, 't Hoen, P A ., Hooft, R, Kuhn, T, Kok, R, Kok, J, Lusher, S J, Martone, M E, Mons, A, Packer, A L, Persson, B, Rocca-Serra, P, Roos, M, van Schaik, R, Sansone, S-A, Schultes, E, Sengstag, T, Slater, T, Strawn, G, Swertz, M A, Thompson, M, van der Lei, J, van Mulligen, E, Velterop, J, Waagmeester, A, Wittenburg, P, Wolstencroft, K, Zhao, J and Mons, B 2016 The FAIR

Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, *Scientific Data*, 3: 160018.

Wuttke, U 2019 “Here be dragons”: Open Access to Research Data in the Humanities. *ulrikewuttke*. Available at <https://ulrikewuttke.wordpress.com/2019/04/09/open-data-humanities/> [Last accessed 17 April 2019].

